

SNT

Direct-to-Satellite IoT: Overview, challenges and potential solutions

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Outline

- IoT and satellite integration
- Direct-to-Satellite IoT challenges
- Techniques for IoT-Satellite integration
- Direct-to-Satellite IoT status
- Takeaways

IoT and satellite integration

- Why IoT-satellite integration is needed?
 - Achieve worldwide coverage
 - Complement terrestrial networks (TNs) in under-served area
 - Address mission-critical services
 - TNs are unavailable
- Direct-to-satellite IoT
 - No need for infrastructure deployment
 - Better profitability compared to indirect-to-satellite IoT for some use cases
 - e.g., absence of infrastructure maintenance, Low device density use cases, mobility...
- Preliminary use-cases
 - Wide area remote monitoring, Smart agriculture, Asset tracking, Marine space, ...

Satellite-IoT network component

- IoT user equipment (IoT-UE)
- Satellite
 - GEO, MEO or LEO
 - Transparent or regenerative
- Satellite gateway (GW)
 - Connect the satellite to the ground infrastructure
 - Control the satellite
- Base station (BS)
 - Packet processing and forwarding to/from the core network
- Core network (i.e., network server)
 - Manage user connections, data traffic routing, and user service delivery
- Data network for IoT application

Architecture options for IoT-Satellite network – *Transparent payload*

Satellite acts as a relay between IoT-UE and the serving base station

Functionalities include signal amplification and re-direction from IoT-UEs (resp. BS) to BS (resp. IoT-UEs)

Architecture options for IoT-Satellite network – *Regenerative payload*

Satellite acts as a base station

Functionalities includes data processing (e.g., filtering, demodulation, decoding, re-encoding, re-modulation)

Direct-to-Satellite IoT challenges

Link budget

- Specific to satellite channel
 - Higher path loss
 - Signal quality & scattering statistics depend on the elevation angle
 - Atmospheric effects (e.g., scintillation)
- IoT-satellite systems should deal with Low SNR values
 - e.g., -3.2 dB
- It is still possible to close the link for most IoT protocols [1,2].

Parameters	Values			
	GEO		LEO (600 km)	
Forward link	DL	UL	DL	UL
Bandwidth [kHz]	180	15	180	15
Free space loss [dB]	190.20	190.20	159.7	159.7
Atmospheric loss [dB]	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1
Shadowing margin [dB]	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Scintillation loss [dB]	2.20	2.20	2.20	2.20
Polarization loss [dB]	3	3	3	3
EIRP [dBW]	59.3	-6.99	34.3	-6.99
G/T [dB/K]	-31.62	19	-31.62	1.1
SNR [dB]	-3.2	-0.35	3	12.95

[3] H. Chougrani, O. Kodheli, W. Martins, H. Chaker and S. Chatzinotas, "PHY aspects of MTC and Satellite Integration," accepted in Integrating Machine-Type-Communication (MTC) and Satellites for IoT: Towards 6G, Wiley and IEEE Press book, 2023, ch. 06

[1] V. Mannoni, V. Berg, S. Cazalens and P. Raveneau, "NB-IoT for Satellite Communications: Physical Layer Analysis and Performance," 2021 IEEE 32nd Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC), Helsinki, Finland, 2021, pp. 1595-1600, doi: 10.1109/PIMRC50174.2021.9569550.

[2] Semtech Corporation. Sx1276/77/78/79 - 137 MHz to 1020 MHz low power long range transceiver. Technical Report WIRELESS & SENSING PROD-UCTS, TS 36.321, May 2020.

Doppler effect

- Doppler is caused by relative motion between satellite and IoT user
- Doppler creates a frequency shift on the received signal over time contributing to the overall carrier frequency offset (CFO)
 - Doppler shift: Shift in the frequency content
 - Doppler rate: variation of Doppler shift over time
- The Doppler effect for satellite-based networks (mainly NGSO) is much stronger compared to terrestrial network
 - Doppler shift up to ± 40 kHz (e.g., LEO at 600 km) vs 1 kHz in TNs
 - Doppler rate up to -500 Hz/s (e.g., LEO at 600 km) vs negligible in TNs

Propagation delay

- TN round trip delay (RTD) is less than 1 ms
- RTD in satellite system \gg RTD in TNs and depends on
 - Satellite orbit (LEO, MEO, GEO)
 - Type of payload (Transparent or regenerative)
 - Elevation angle
- Delay rate is the variation of the delay over time
 - +/- 40 us/s for LEO @ 600km
- Some quantitative values in the satellite system
 - Transparent payload @ 10 degrees elev. Angle (both user and feeder links)
 - Up to 542 ms RTD in GEO @36000 km
 - Up to 187 ms for MEO @10000 km
 - Up to 26 ms for LEO @600 km
 - RTDs in regenerative payloads are half of the above values

Example of propagation delay in a transparent payload configuration

Direct-to-Satellite IoT impact

Impact of satellite-IoT integration

- Increase the receiver complexity and power consumption
 - Higher time for synchronization due to the longer receiving windows
 - Many frequency-binned searches
- Degradation or even failure of the access procedures (specific to NB-IoT)
 - Cyclic prefix may be insufficient to cope with higher RTD
 - Loss of orthogonality
 - Expiry of protocol timers
- Degradation of the reception performance
 - Bad synchronization performance
 - SNR degradation
 - Inter-carrier interference & user collision
- Risk of loss of time/freq. synchronization due to delay/Doppler rate
- Decrease the spectral efficiency
 - More pilots are needed to cope with lower channel coherence time
- Increase the cost of deployment
 - Due to the need for larger frequency bands to cope with a high range of frequency uncertainty
- Higher latencies (usually not an issue for IoT applications)

Techniques for IoT-satellite integration

UE location-aware scheme 1/2

- Objective:
 - Compensate the Doppler and propagation delay experienced between the UE and the satellite
 - The compensation is not required to be perfect but good enough to reduce the delay and Doppler to values similar to what is experienced in IoT-TN
- Concept:
 - Predict the delay and Doppler experienced between the UE and the Satellite at the UE level
- Requirements
 - Two pieces of information are required at the UE level
 - satellite ephemeris: broadcasted by the satellite to UEs
 - Location of the UE: known a priori for fixed UEs or using GNSS for mobile UEs

UE location-aware scheme 2/2

- How

- Ephemeris information → (a) UE predicts the location and instantaneous velocity of the satellite at any time
- (b) UE gets its location and velocity (GNSS for mobile UEs)
- (a) + (b) → (c) UE deduces relative velocity and distance
- (c) → UE calculates the Doppler and propagation delay

✓ UE compensates Doppler and delay when transmitting or receiving packets

- Cons

- GNSS consumes power which is not suitable for low-power IoT use cases
- Not always available (indoor, polar regions)

This solution is adopted by 3GPP in Release 17 & 18

Beam-level Doppler & delay compensation 1/3

- Objective

- Pre/post compensation of the Doppler and propagation delay experienced between the UE and the satellite
- The compensation is not required to be perfect but good enough to reduce the delay and Doppler to values similar to what is experienced in IoT-TN

- Concept

- Predict the Doppler (resp. delay) onboard the satellite at the center of each beam (resp. closest point on earth)

- Requirements

- Satellite ephemeris knowledge
- Beam layout knowledge: known by design

Beam-level Doppler & delay compensation 2/3

• How

- Ephemeris information + beam center location → (a) satellite predicts the relative velocity between itself and the center of each beam
- (a) → satellite calculates the Doppler and compensates it when transmitting or receiving packets
- Ephemeris information + beam layout → (b) satellite predicts the distance between itself and the closest point on earth in the satellite beam coverage
- (b) → (c) satellite broadcast this value as a common delay (CD) for all UEs within the beam
- UE consider the CD when transmitting packets

Beam-level Doppler & delay compensation 3/3

- Cons

- The closest point on earth may depend on the ground relief and/or UE types (e.g., aircraft altitude) which increase further the residual frequency and time offsets
- Residual frequency and time offsets may still be larger compared to the ones encountered in TNs
 - Increase complexity
 - Degrade the performance
- The solution depends on the beam size (smaller beams are required)
 - Frequent handovers
 - Dedicated antenna technology

This solution is adopted by several companies (e.g., AST mobile, Lynk and potentially STARLINK)

IoT direct-to-satellite status

Status of IoT-direct direct-to-satellite connectivity

- 3GPP provides specifications for NB-IoT and satellite integration starting from release 17
- Several successful tests of IoT-satellite integration were done recently
 - 2020 successful field trial of NB-IoT via satellite (MediaTek together with Inmarsat)
 - 2022 LoRa device tested with a NORBY CubeSat operating at 560-km altitude (see ref. [4])
- Several startups are presents
 - 3GPP-based solutions: OQTechnology, Sateliot, Lynk
 - Proprietary solutions: Kinéis, Astrocast, DENMACH,...

[4] A. M. Zadorozhny et al., "First Flight-Testing of LoRa Modulation in Satellite Radio Communications in Low-Earth Orbit," in IEEE Access, vol. 10, pp. 100006-100023, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3207762.

Status of IoT-direct direct-to-satellite connectivity

- In 2023 few early products start to appear in the market
 - MT6825 from MediaTek (<https://www.mediatek.com/products/5g-ntn/mt6825>)
 - ALT1250 from SONY (<https://altair.sony-semicon.com/products/alt1250/>)
 - Quectel BG770 from Quectel (<https://www.quectel.com/news-and-pr/quectel-amarisoft-support-ntn-adoption>)

Takeaways

Takeaways

- Satellites are a must
 - TNs can not guarantee worldwide coverage
- Satellite-IoT integration is possible
 - New Business opportunities
- Solutions are proposed but still some limitations
 - Availability & cost of GNSS use
 - IoT device complexity and power consumption
- Lightweight energy-efficient solutions for IoT-satellite are needed
- Seamless TN-NTN IoT integration should be the objective in the future
 - The same HW should be used
- Startups should adopt sparse constellation to reduce cost and be competitive

Thank you

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